

Adventures in Data Citation: deadly *E. coli* outbreaks, Sorghum and RNA- editomes provide examples for the future.

doi:10.5524/100012

DataCite Summer meeting
14th June 2012, Copenhagen

Scott Edmunds

www.gigasciencejournal.com

Overview

A brief history of genomics...

Human Genome Project: 1990-2003.

1 Genome = \$3 Billion

Source: http://www.genome.gov/Images/press_photos/highres/38-300.jpg

A brief history of genomics...

Source: <http://www.genome.gov/sequencingcosts/> (with apologies)

A brief history of genomics...

Source: <http://www.genome.gov/sequencingcosts/> (with apologies)

A brief history of genomics...

Source: <http://www.genome.gov/sequencingcosts/> (with apologies)

- Formerly known as Beijing Genomics Institute
- Founded in 1999 (1% of HGP)
- Not-for-profit research institute funded by commercial sequencing-as-a-service
- Now the largest genomic organization in the world
- Goal
 - Use genomics technology to impact the society
 - Make leading edge genomics highly accessible to the global research community

Global, with HQ in Shenzhen

BGI's branches have been extended to worldwide.

Global, with HQ in Shenzhen

Locations

BGI's branches have been extended to worldwide.

Global Sequencing Capacity

Next Generation Genomics: World Map of High-throughput Sequencers

Show all platforms Illumina GA2 Illumina HiSeq Illumina MiSeq Ion Torrent PacBio Polonator Roche/454 SOLID Service Provider

Next Generation

Show all platform

Sequencers

- 137** Illumina/HiSeq 2000
- 27** LifeTech/SOLiD 4
- 1** 454 GS FLX+
- 2** Illumina iScan
- 1** Illumina MiSeq
- 1** Ion Torrent

Data Production

5.6 Tb / day
 > 1500X of human genome / day

Multiple Supercomputing Centers

157 TB Flops
 20 TB Memory
 14.7 PB Storage

運行中
Running

Illumina

Goal – “Just sequence it.”

M+M+M: Million Genome Projects

- Plant and Animal Genomes: G10K, i5K...
- Variation Genomes: 10K rice resequencing...
- Human Genomes: Ancient, Population, Medical
- Cell Genomes: cancer single cell
- Micro Ecosystems: Metahit, EMP, etc.
- Personal Genomes

Sequencing of Life

BGI Goes Denmark

BGI Goes Denmark

Proposals:

International Aquatic Mammals Genome Project

International Sturgeon
Genome Project

Genomics: the data-sharing success story?:

Sharing/reproducibility helped by stability of:

1. Platforms

1st Gen

2nd Gen

1. Repositories

EMBL-EBI

2. Standards

Genomics Data Sharing Policies...

Bermuda Accords 1996/1997/1998:

1. Automatic release of sequence assemblies within **24 hours**.
2. Immediate publication of finished annotated sequences.
3. Aim to make the entire sequence freely available in the **public domain** for both research and development in order to maximise benefits to society.

Fort Lauderdale Agreement, 2003:

1. Sequence traces from whole genome shotgun projects are to be deposited in a trace archive within **one week** of production.
2. Whole genome assemblies are to be deposited in a public nucleotide sequence database **as soon as possible** after the assembled sequence has met a set of quality evaluation criteria.

Toronto International data release workshop, 2009:

The goal was to reaffirm and refine, where needed, the policies related to the early release of genomic data, and to extend, if possible, similar data release policies to other types of large biological datasets – whether from proteomics, biobanking or metabolite research.

Challenges for the future...

(A) Cumulative base pairs in INSDC over time, excluding the Trace Archive.

(B) Base pairs in INSDC, broken down into selected data components.

Challenges for the future...

1. Data Volumes (transfer, backlogs, funding issues)

2. Compliance

3. Lack of interoperability/sufficient metadata

4. Long tail of curation (“Democratization” of “big-data”)

New incentives/credit

Credit where credit is overdue:

“One option would be to provide researchers who release data to public repositories with a means of accreditation.”

“An ability to search the literature for all online papers that used a particular data set would enable appropriate attribution for those who share. “

Nature Biotechnology **27**, 579 (2009)

Prepublication data sharing

(Toronto International Data Release Workshop)

“Data producers benefit from creating a citable reference, as it can later be used to reflect impact of the data sets.”

Nature **461**, 168-170 (2009)

New incentives/credit = Data Citation?

“increase acceptance of research data as legitimate, citable contributions to the scholarly record”.

“data generated in the course of research are just as valuable to the ongoing academic discourse as papers and monographs”.

First issue next month...

(GIGA)ⁿ SCIENCE

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Papers in the era of big-data

(GIGA)ⁿ
SCIENCE

goal: Executable Research Objects

Citable DOI

Adventures in Data Citation

doi:10.5524/100001

doi>

For data citation to work, needs:

1. Proven utility/potential user base.
2. Acceptance/inclusion by journals.
3. Data+Citation: inclusion in the references.
4. Tracking by citation indexes.
5. Usage of the metrics by the community...

Datacitation 1: utility/user base.

Establishment of data DOIs and use by databases:

Shackleton NJ, Hall MA, Vincent E (2001): **Mean stable carbon isotope ratios of Cibicidoides wuellerstorfi from sediment core MD95-2042 on the Iberian margin, North Atlantic.** *PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science*. <http://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.58229>

Cited in:

Pahnke K, Zahn R: **Southern Hemisphere Water Mass Conversion Linked with North Atlantic Climate Variability.** *Science* 2005, **307**:1741 -1746.

Nocek B, Xu X, Savchenko A, Edwards A, Joachimiak A. 2007. PDB ID: 2P06 Crystal structure of a predicted coding region AF_0060 from *Archaeoglobus fulgidus* DSM 4304. 10.2210/pdb2p06/pdb.

Cited in:

Andreeva A, Howorth D, Chandonia J-M, Brenner SE, Hubbard TJP, Chothia C, Murzin AG: **Data growth and its impact on the SCOP database: new developments.** *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2008, **36**:D419-425.

(GIGA)ⁿ DB

BGI Datasets Get DOI[®]s

Many released pre-publication...

Invertebrate

Ant

- Florida carpenter ant
- Jerdon's jumping ant
- Leaf-cutter ant

Roundworm

Schistosoma

Silkworm

1000 Genomes

A Deep Catalog of Human Genetic Variation

Human

Asian individual (YH)

- DNA Methylome
- Genome Assembly
- **Transcriptome**

Cancer (14TB)

Ancient DNA

- Saqqaq Eskimo
- Aboriginal Australian

华大基因
BGI

Vertebrates

Giant panda Macaque

- Chinese rhesus
- Crab-eating

Mini-Pig

Naked mole rat

Penguin

- Emperor penguin
- Adelle penguin

Pigeon, domestic

Polar bear

Sheep

Tibetan antelope

Microbe

E. Coli O104:H4 TY-2482

Cell-Line

Chinese Hamster Ovary

PLANTS

Chinese cabbage

Cucumber

Foxtail millet

Pigeonpea

Potato

Sorghum

Our first DOI:

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Ecoli: TY-2482

E. coli O104: H4 sequence from the 2011 outbreak

To maximize its utility to the research community and aid those fighting the current epidemic, genomic data is released here into the public domain under a CC0 license. Until the publication of research papers on the assembly and whole-genome analysis of this isolate we would ask you to cite this dataset as:

Li, D; Xi, F; Zhao, M; Liang, Y; Chen, W; Cao, S; Xu, R; Wang, G; Wang, J; Zhang, Z; Li, Y; Cui, Y; Chang, C; Cui, C; Luo, Y; Qin, J; Li, S; Li, J; Peng, Y; Pu, F; Sun, Y; Chen, Y; Zong, Y; Ma, X; Yang, X; Cen, Z; Zhao, X; Chen, F; Yin, X; Song, Y; Rohde, H; Li, Y; Wang, J; Wang, J and the Escherichia coli O104:H4 TY-2482 isolate genome sequencing consortium (2011)

Genomic data from *Escherichia coli* O104:H4 isolate TY-2482. BGI Shenzhen. doi:10.5524/100001

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100001>

To the extent possible under law, BGI Shenzhen has waived all copyright and related or neighboring rights to Genomic Data from the 2011 E. coli outbreak. This work is published from: China.

E. Coli #crowdsourcing: the first **tweenome**?

The screenshot shows a Twitter profile for 'BGI_Events' (BGI Shenzhen). The profile has 952 tweets, 509 following, and 609 followers. The main content is a timeline of tweets related to the EHEC genome project. The tweets include:

- A tweet from BGI_Events (2 Jun) announcing the upload of the new #EHEC strain sequence to NCBI (SRA037315.1) and providing a link to ftp://ftp.genomics.org.cn/pub/Ecoli_TY-2482 #Ecoli.
- A tweet from pathogenomenick (2 Jun) stating they've done a first pass assembly of the BGI Ion Torrent E. coli data with MIRA, with N50 = 3675, and providing a link to http://bit.ly/IXO60t.
- A tweet from marina_manrique (3 Jun) mentioning that Era7 Bioinformatics annotated the E coli strain of EU outbreak, with a link to http://bit.ly/kolMjd and tagging @BGI_Events and @pathogenomenick #EHEC.
- A tweet from NCBI Staff (3 Jun) stating that NCBI's SRA database contains genome sequence reads of the strain suspected of causing the European E. coli outbreak, with a link to http://1.usa.gov/kldix4.
- A tweet from BGI_Events (5 Jun) stating that crowdsourced #EHEC genome data is getting organized with @marina_manrique's Github repository at http://ow.ly/5af5p and wiki at http://ow.ly/5af5j.

The right sidebar shows 'Who to follow' with suggestions for IrishCentral, MPPjournal, and marcoscarvalho. The 'Trends' section lists various hashtags and topics like #hpveer, #whenihadamyspace, #thanksjustin, #dontlookatmeif, LuanSnossoNamorado, Lemonade Mouth, and Last Friday Night.

E. Coli #crowdsourcing: the first **tweenome**?

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E.coli O104:H4 Genome Analysis Crowdsourcing

[New Page](#) | [Edit Page](#) | [Page History](#)

In this wiki we aim to gather all the results of the analysis of the *E. coli* O104:H4 strain responsible for the current outbreak in Germany and Europe.

NINE isolates from the outbreak have been sequenced so far:

- TY2482 (BGI in collaboration with University Medical Centre Hamburg-Eppendorf)
- LB226692 (Life Tech in-house in collaboration with University of Muenster)
- 5 isolates: H112180280 (released earlier with 454 scaffold) plus 4 additional isolates (Health Protection Agency, Colindale, UK)
- 2 isolates, unnamed (Göttingen Genomics Lab, Germany)

A historical O104:H4 ST678 isolate from 2001 has also been sequenced by Univ. Hospital Muenster and Life Tech but data not available.

Sequence reads

E. Coli #crowdsourcing: the first **tweenome**?

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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

BRIEF REPORT

Open-Source Genomic Analysis of Shiga-Toxin–Producing *E. coli* O104:H4

Holger Rohde, M.D., Junjie Qin, Ph.D., Yujun Cui, Ph.D., Dongfang Li, M.E., Nicholas J. Loman, M.B., B.S., Moritz Hentschke, M.D., Wentong Chen, B.S., Fei Pu, B.S., Yangqing Peng, B.S., Junhua Li, B.E., Feng Xi, B.E., Shenghui Li, B.S., Yin Li, B.S., Zhaoxi Zhang, B.S., Xianwei Yang, B.S., Meiru Zhao, M.S., Peng Wang, B.M., Yuanlin Guan, B.E., Zhong Cen, M.E., Xiangna Zhao, B.S., Martin Christner, M.D., Robin Kobbe, M.D., Sebastian Loos, M.D., Jun Oh, M.D., Liang Yang, Ph.D., Antoine Danchin, Ph.D., George F. Gao, Ph.D., Yajun Song, Ph.D., Yingrui Li, B.S., Huanming Yang, Ph.D., Jian Wang, Ph.D., Jianguo Xu, M.D., Ph.D., Mark J. Pallen, M.D., Ph.D., Jun Wang, Ph.D., Martin Aepfelbacher, M.D., Ruifu Yang, M.D., Ph.D., and the *E. coli* O104:H4 Genome Analysis Crowd-Sourcing Consortium

July 27, 2011 (10.1056/NEJMoa1107643)

E. Coli #crowdsourcing: Downstream consequences:

1. Therapeutics (primers, antimicrobials) 2. Platform Comparisons (Loman et al., Nature Biotech 2012)

3. Speed/legal-freedom

NATURE | NEWS

Open-data project aims to ease the way for genomic research

A revamped approach to informed consent will liberate data for science, developers say.

Erika Check Hayden

25 April 2012

“Last summer, biologist Andrew Kasarskis was eager to help decipher the genetic origin of the Escherichia coli strain that infected roughly 4,000 people in Germany between May and July. But he knew it that might take days for the lawyers at his company — Pacific Biosciences — to parse the agreements governing how his team could use data collected on the strain. **Luckily, one team had released its data under a Creative Commons licence that allowed free use of the data**, allowing Kasarskis and his colleagues to join the international research effort and **publish their work without wasting time on legal wrangling.**”

Data Citation 2: acceptance by journals

F1000Research

OPEN SCIENCE • OPEN DATA • OPEN PEER REVIEW

JOURNAL POLICIES

Journals and publishers that have confirmed that they would not view publication of datasets with a DOI and associated protocol information as prior publication, if a more standard (analysis/conclusions) article based on the data was subsequently submitted to them:

- » BMC journals
- » BMJ Group journals
- » Elsevier journals
- » IOS Press journals
- » The Lancet journals
- » Nature-titled journals
- » PLoS journals
- » RSC journals
- » SAGE journals
- » *Adv Clin Neurosci Rehabil*
- » *Bioinformatics*
- » *Cardiovasc Ther*
- » *Ecol Lett*
- » *Eur J Neurosci*
- » *Int J Obstet Anesth*
- » *J Clin Invest*
- » *J Eat Disord*
- » *J Neurol*
- » *J Neurosci*
- » *J Pain*
- » *J Plant Ecol*
- » *Neurorol Urodyn*
- » *New Engl J Med*
- » *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*
- » *PROTEOMICS J*
- » *Science*

Respondents that would see the publication of data with a DOI and protocol information as potential prior publication:

- » Cell Press journals
- » *Ann Oncol*

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NATURE BIOTECHNOLOGY | RESEARCH | LETTER OPEN

Genome sequencing and comparison of two primate animal models, the cynomolgus and rhesus macaques

Guangmei Yan, Guojie Zhang, Xiaodong Fang, Yanfeng Zhang, Cai Li, Fei Li, Li, Yan Li, Alain J van Gool, Hongli Du, Jiesi Chen, Ronghua Chen, Pei Zhang, R Thompson, Yuhuan Meng, Yingli Bai, Jufang Wang, Min Zhou, Tao Wang, Y Jianwen Li, Zhiwen Wang *et al.*

Affiliations | Contributions | Corresponding authors

Nature Biotechnology 29, 1019–1023 (2011) | doi:10.1038/nbt.1992
Received 08 March 2011 | Accepted 31 August 2011 | Published online 16 October 2011

carried out a population survey in 33 unrelated CE macaque individuals of Vietnamese origin and 28 CR macaque individuals using PCR amplification and sequencing.

Accession codes.
The CR macaque (*M. mulatta*) and the CE macaque (*M. fascicularis*) whole genome shotgun projects have been deposited at DDBJ/EMBL/GenBank under the accession numbers [AEHK0000000](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000) and [AEHL0000000](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000). The versions described in this Letter are [AEHK01000000](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000) and [AEHL01000000](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000). All short read data have been deposited into the Short Read Archive under accession numbers [SRA023855](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000) and [SRA023856](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000). Raw sequencing data of transcriptome have been deposited in Gene Expression Omnibus as [GSE29629](https://doi.org/10.5554/1000000). Genome assemblies are also available using the following data DOIs at our CLIMB repository: doi:10.5524/100002 and doi:10.5524/100003 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100002>> and <<http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100003>>.

Accession codes

Main • Methods • Accession codes • References • Acknowledgments • Author information • Supplementary information

Referenced accessions

DNA Data Bank of Japan	Gene Expression Omnibus	Sequence Read Archive
AEHK00000000	GSE29629	SRA023855
AEHL00000000		SRA023856

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Home > Science Magazine > 7 October 2011 > Rasmussen *et al.* | 334 (6052): 94–98

Published Online September 22 2011
Science 7 October 2011.
Vol. 334 no. 6052 pp. 94–98
DOI: 10.1126/science.1211177

ADVERTISMENT

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VERSION HISTORY

- 334/6052/94 (most recent)
- science.1211177v1

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29. Acknowledgments: Our work was endorsed by the Goldfields Land and Sea Council, the organization representing the Aboriginal Traditional Owners of the Goldfields region, including the cultural (and possibly the biological) descendants of the individual who provided the hair sample. See (4) for letter. Data are accessible through NCBI Sequence Read Archive SRA035301.1 or through <http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100010>. We note the following additional affiliations: S.T. also works for the Australian Federal Police; J.D. is a partner in Dortch & Cuthbert Pty. Ltd.; P.F. is director of Genetic Ancestor Ltd. and Fluxus Technology Ltd.; and C.D.B. serves as an unpaid consultant for 23andMe. For author contributions and extended acknowledgements, see (4).

REPORT

An Aboriginal Australian Genome into Asia

Morten Rasmussen^{1,2,4}, Xiaosen Guo^{2,3,4}, Yong Wan^{1,2,4}, Anders Albrechtsen⁵, Line Skotte⁶, Stinus Lindgreen⁷, Toomas Kivisild⁸, Weiwei Zhai^{1,9}, Anders Eriksson¹⁰, Francisco M. De La Vega¹¹, Silvana Tridico¹², Ene M. J. Victor Moreno-Mayari¹³, Craig Muller¹⁴, Joe Dorcas¹⁵, Peter Forster¹⁶, Peter Krause¹⁷, Agata Wesolowska¹⁸, Monika Karmin¹⁹, Lucy A. Weinert²⁰, Bo Wang²¹, Jun Li²², Shuishuai Tai²³, Fei Xiao²⁴, Tsunehiko Hanihara²⁵, George van Driem²⁶, Aashish R. Jha²⁷, François-Xavier Ricaut²⁸, Peter de Knijff²⁹, Andrea B. Migliano³⁰, Irene Gallego Romero³¹, Karsten Kristiansen^{32,33}, David M. Lambert³⁴, Søren Brunak^{35,36}, Peter Forster^{37,38}, Bernd Brinkmann³⁹, Olaf Nehlich⁴⁰, Michael Bunce⁴¹, Michael Richards^{42,43}, Ramneek Gupta⁴⁴, Carlos D. Bustamante⁴⁵, Anders Krogh⁴⁶, Robert A. Foley⁴⁷

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Sweet and grain sorghums

Sorghum is produced globally as a source of food, feed, fiber, and fuel. Grain and sweet sorghums differ in a number of important traits including stem sugar and juice accumulation, plant height, and the production of grain and biomass. The first sorghum whole-genome sequences are now available for analysis, but additional genomic sequences will be required to study genome-wide and intraspecific variation for dissecting the genetic basis of these important traits and for tailor-designed breeding of this important C4 crop.

BGI resequenced two sweet and one grain sorghum inbred lines: E-Tian, JI2731, and Keller.

E-Tian (literally meaning Russian Sweet in Chinese) is a sweet sorghum line introduced into China in the early 1970's. JI2731 is a Chinese kaoliang grain sorghum that is well adapted to Northeast China.

Keller is an American-bred elite sweet sorghum line shown to perform well across a wide range of environmental conditions.

Using the re-sequencing data, a set of nearly 1,500 genes differentiating sweet and grain sorghum were identified. These genes fall into 10 major metabolic pathways involved in sugar and starch metabolisms, lignin and coumarin biosynthesis, nucleic acid metabolism, stress responses and DNA damage repair. In addition, 1,057,018 SNPs, 99,948 indels of 1-10bp in length and 16,487 presence/absence variations were uncovered, and 17,111 CNVs were detected. The majority of the SNPs, large-effect SNPs, indels and presence/absence variations resided in genes containing leucine rich repeats, PPR repeats and disease resistance R genes possessing diverse biological functions or under diversifying selection, but were absent in genes which are essential for life.

This is the first publicly available data that allows the identification of genome-wide patterns of genetic variation in sorghum. The high-density SNP and indel markers presented here will be a valuable resource for future genotype and phenotype studies and the molecular breeding of this important crop and for related species.

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All files

ftp://climb.genomics.cn/pub/Giga/Genome/Poales/Sorghum_bicolor/10.5524/100012/

For further information

[Readme](#)

Assemblies

[E-Tian_CDS.fa](#)

[E-Tian.contig](#)

[E-Tian.gff](#)

Citation

In accordance with our terms of use please cite this dataset as:

Zheng L-Y, Guo X-S, He B, Sun L-J, Peng Y, Dong S-S, Liu T-F, Jiang S, Ramachandran S, Liu C-M, Jing H-C: Genome data from sweet and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*). GigaScience (2011). doi:10.5524/100012

Sweet and grain sorghums

Sorghum is produced globally as a source of food, feed, fiber, and fuel. Grain and sweet sorghums differ in a number of important traits including stem sugar and juice accumulation, plant height, and the production of grain and biomass. The first sorghum whole-genome sequences are now available for analysis, but additional genomic sequences will be required to study genome-wide and locus-specific variation for dissecting the genetic architecture of this important crop. We have resequenced two sweet and one grain sorghum inbred lines: E-Tian, Ji2731, and Keller. E-Tian (literally meaning Russian Sweet in Chinese) is a sweet sorghum line introduced into China in the early 1970s. Ji2731 is a Chinese kaoliang grain sorghum that is well adapted to Northeast China. Keller is an American-bred elite sweet sorghum line shown to perform well in a range of environmental conditions.

- Data submitted to NCBI databases:

- Raw data [SRA:SRA046843](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRA046843)
- Assemblies of 3 strains [Genbank:AHA000000000-AHAQ000000000](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/AHA000000000-AHAQ000000000)
- SNPs [dbSNP:1056306](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/dbSNP/1056306)
- CNVs
- InDels [dbVAR:nstd63](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/dbVAR/nstd63)
- SV

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Zheng L-Y, Guo X-S, He B, Sun L-J, Peng Y,
Dong S-S, Liu T-F, Jiang S, Ramachandran S,
Liu C-M, Jing H-C: Genome data from sweet
and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*).
GigaScience (2011). doi:10.5524/100012

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- Submission to public databases complemented by its citable form in *GigaDB* ([doi:10.5524/100012](https://doi.org/10.5524/100012)).

RESEARCH

Open Access

Genome-wide patterns of genetic variation in sweet and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*)

Lei-Ying Zheng^{1†}, Xiao-Sen Guo^{2†}, Bing He^{2†}, Lian-Jun Sun^{1†}, Yao Peng², Shan-Shan Dong², Teng-Fei Liu², Shuye Jiang^{1,3}, Srinivasan Ramachandran^{1,3}, Chun-Ming Liu¹ and Hai-Chun Jing^{1*}

Abstract

Background: Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) is globally produced as a source of food, feed, fiber and fuel. Grain and sweet sorghums differ in a number of important traits, including stem sugar and juice accumulation, plant height as well as grain and biomass production. The first whole genome sequence of a grain sorghum is available, but additional genome sequences are required to study genome-wide and intraspecific variation for dissecting the genetic basis of these important traits and for tailor-designed breeding of this important C₄ crop.

Results: We resequenced two sweet and one grain sorghum inbred lines, and identified a set of nearly 1,500 genes differentiating sweet and grain sorghum. These genes fall into ten major metabolic pathways involved in sugar and starch metabolisms, lignin and coumarin biosynthesis, nucleic acid metabolism, stress responses and DNA damage repair. In addition, we uncovered 1,057,018 SNPs, 99,948 indels of 1 to 10 bp in length and 16,487 presence/absence variations as well as 17,111 copy number variations. The majority of the large-effect SNPs, indels and presence/absence variations resided in the genes containing leucine rich repeats, PPR repeats and disease resistance *R* genes possessing diverse biological functions or under diversifying selection, but were absent in genes that are essential for life.

Conclusions: This is a first report of the identification of genome-wide patterns of genetic variation in sorghum. High-density SNP and indel markers reported here will be a valuable resource for future gene-phenotype studies and the molecular breeding of this important crop and related species.

RESEARCH

Genome sweet a

Lei-Ying Zheng^{1†},
Shuye Jiang^{1,2,3}, Sri

Abstract

Background: Sorghum is a source of sweet sorghums as well as grain sorghums. We have identified an additional genomic region and its genetic basis of sweet sorghum.

Results: We resequenced the genomes of sweet sorghum and identified genes differential for sugar and starch synthesis, DNA damage repair, presence/absence of R genes and presence/absence of disease resistance R genes that are essential for sweet sorghum.

Conclusions: This study shows that high-density SNP and the molecular

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doi:10.1186/gb-2011-12-11-r114
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RESEARCH

Genome-wide patterns of genetic variation in sweet and grain sorghum

Lei-Ying Zheng^{1†},
Shuye Jiang^{1,2}, Sri

Abstract

Background: Sorghum is a major crop for bioenergy and food. Sweet sorghums are used as a source of sugar and grain sorghums as a source of grain and forage.

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Comprehensive analysis of RNA-Seq data reveals extensive RNA editing in a human transcriptome

Zhiyu Peng, Yanbing Cheng, Bertrand Chin-Ming Tan, Lin Kang, Zhijian Tian, Yuankun Zhu, Wenwei Zhang, Yu Liang, Xueda Hu, Xuemei Tan, Jing Guo, Zirui Dong, Yan Liang, Li Bao & Jun Wang

[Affiliations](#) | [Contributions](#) | [Corresponding author](#)

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Abstract

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RNA editing is a post-transcriptional event that recodes hereditary information. Here we describe a comprehensive profile of the RNA editome of a male Han Chinese individual based on analysis of ~767 million sequencing reads from poly(A)⁺, poly(A)⁻ and small RNA samples. We developed a computational pipeline that carefully controls for false positives while calling RNA editing

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Abstract

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**...the final
challenge?**

Data Citation in the Wild

Valerie Enriquez^{1,2}, Sarah Walker Judson^{1,3}, Nicholas M. Weber^{1,4}

and mentors Suzie Allard^{1,5}, Robert B. Cook^{1,5}, Heather A. Plowowar^{1,7}, Robert J. Sandusky^{1,8}, Todd J. Vision^{1,7,9}, Bruce Wilson^{1,2,4}

Data attribution is important

- Rewards those who contribute
- Allows measurement of reuse to demonstrate value and evaluate policy

How is data reuse currently attributed?

We investigated the policies, practices, and implications of data attribution practices in the environmental sciences.

Policies

We reviewed policies of various stakeholders within the environmental sciences, looking for *evidence of data citation policies* and *attribution suggestions*.

Policies in our sample that mention data citation

Repositories	8 of 26,	31%
Journals	16 of 307,	6%
Funders	1 of 52,	2%

Repository instructions varied. Several patterns:

GenBank Requirements
Publicly available sequences are available on the public domain and are not subject to copyright. However, the user must acknowledge the source of the data and the contribution of the user to the project.

Open Access Policy
The user must acknowledge the source of the data and the contribution of the user to the project.

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If the user has data deposited from the Earth Research Data Archive (ERDA) and incorporated into your research, please provide the following acknowledgment in your published work: "These data and research were provided by the Earth Research Data Archive (ERDA), funded by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE), Earth Research Data Archive and Science (ERDA) Center, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720."

Examples: Dryad, SDG/GenBank, IGDAC, ORNL DAAC

Journal policy content also varied:

- how to hyperlink accession numbers,
- which databases are permitted in reference list,
- style guide for dataset references, ...

Practices

We reviewed 500 articles in six leading environmental science, ecology and evolutionary biology journals, 2000-2010. **Data attribution patterns** varied widely in the main body of articles (n=221):

Mentioned author ref	Mentioned repository	Mentioned dataset ID	Pattern frequency
✓			17%
✓	✓		22%
✓	✓	✓	36%
✓	✓		12%
✓	✓	✓	7%
✓	✓	✓	5%
53%	47%	13%	

The references used to build this database are available in the appendix.

cases and different scenarios of fossil calibrations. GenBank accession numbers can be found in the original publications.

We reanalyzed the Barro Colorado Island (BCI) permanent forest plot data in order to learn about the

82. Cooper et al. 2005
348. Peery 2007
... Shuller and Whitford 1980; Peery 2007

Species	US-OTU4
<i>Platypharax antonia</i>	AF483000
<i>Rhaphidophora</i>	AF483001
<i>Alouatta palliata</i>	AF483002
<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	AF483003

(GenBank Accession: new EU073092-EU073150) were downloaded into BioEdit and compared to those in

was obtained from Genbank, accession number L19324; Greenhalgh et al. 1993. Specimens sequenced are listed

Meteorological data were obtained from the North Carolina State Climate Service (North Carolina State Climate Office 2008) for the six weather stations surrounding Dar-

North Carolina State Climate Office. 2008. NC Climate Retrieval and Observations Network of the Inportant database. <http://www.nc-climate.com/obs/obs.htm>. Accessed February 23, 2009.
Novick, K., F. Steg, G. G. Karl, D. S. Elsworth, M. Legler, J. Jiang.

Implications

Because of tool limitations and these diverse data attribution practices, tracking dataset reuse is prohibitively complicated:

We found that data citation best practices are rarely mentioned, and attribution practice is very diverse.

As a result of diverse practices and tool limitations, data citations are currently very difficult to track.

Data Citation in the Wild

Valerie Enriquez^{1,2}, Sarah Walker Judson^{1,3}, Nicholas M. Weber^{1,4}

Datacitation 5: metrics?

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7%
5%

I'm afraid we are making promises to data creators about attribution and reward that we can't keep. "Make your data citeable!" is the cry. Ok. So citeable is step one. Cited is step two. But for the citation to be useful, it has to be indexed so that citation metrics can be tracked and admired and used.

Who is indexing data citations right now? As far as I can tell: absolutely no one.

We found that data citation best practices are rarely mentioned, and practices are diverse.

As a result of diverse practices and tool limitations, data citations are currently very difficult to track.

Where data citation is in 2012:

1. Proven utility/potential user base. ✓
2. Acceptance/inclusion by journals. ✓
3. Data+Citation: inclusion in the references. ✓
4. Tracking by citation indexes. X
5. Usage of the metrics by the community... X

Minor quibbles: export to citation managers

DCC/DataCite recommended format:

Zheng, L-Y; Guo, X-S; He, B; Sun, L-J; Peng, Y; Dong, S-S; Liu, T-F; Jiang, S; Ramachandran, S; Liu, C-M; Jing, H-C; (2011): Genome data from sweet and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*); GigaScience. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100012>

zotero formatting:

Zheng, L-Y (2011). Genome data from sweet and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*). GigaScience. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100012>

Mendeley formatting:

Zheng L-Y ; Guo X-S ; He B ; Sun L-J ; Peng Y ; Dong S-S ; Liu T-F ; Jiang S ; Ramachandran S ; Liu C-M ; Jing H-C: **Genome data from sweet and grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*)**. 2011.

Minor quibbles: clearer guidelines

Rules for versioning/where do you set granularity?

Data standardization, sharing and publication

Edited by: Dr Craig Hooker, Dr Heather Piwowar, Dr David Shotton

Collection published: 26 January 2011

Last updated: 9 May 2012

This series aims to promote best practice in data sharing and publication through data standardization. This ongoing collection brings together articles describing domain-specific data standards and how to implement them, providing or linking to a reference data set prepared and formatted to serve as an example.

BMC Research Notes is [collaborating](#) with [BioSharing](#) to develop a [comprehensive catalogue](#) of domain-specific data standards across biology and medicine, which will include a number of the exemplary data notes in this article collection.

The series also encompasses articles on broader aspects of scientific data sharing, archiving, and open data. This series aims to encourage sharing and publication of data in re-usable and harvestable formats by increasing awareness of existing and emerging data standards and best practices. Contributions to the series are welcome from all fields of biology and medicine and you can [contact](#) *BMC Research Notes*' editorial team and read our call for [contributions](#) for more information.

Correspondence [Open Access](#) [Highly accessed](#)

Adventures in data citation: sorghum genome data exemplifies the new gold standard

Scott C Edmunds, Tom J Pollard, Brian Hole, Alexandra Basford

BMC Research Notes 2012, **5**:223 (9 May 2012)

[Abstract](#) | [Provisional PDF](#) | [PubMed](#) | [► Editor's summary](#)

The future of DNA sequence archiving

Guy Cochrane*, Charles E Cook and Ewan Birney

Abstract

Archives operating under the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration currently preserve all submitted sequences equally, but rapid increases in the rate of global sequence production will soon require differentiated treatment of DNA sequences submitted for archiving. Here, we provide a background on the establishment and operation of public data repositories and present the issues the community faces given the current overwhelming increase in data output. We also propose a way forward through the use a graded system in which the ease of reproduction of a sequencing-based experiment and the relative availability of a sample for resequencing be used as a means to define the level of lossy compression to the stored data.

Keywords DNA, sequence, archive, compression, storage, image

The vast majority of living organisms utilise nucleic acid as their primary store of genetic information. The technology to sequence DNA routinely was developed in the 1970s, but advances over time have since reduced cost and increased output. As the cost of sequencing has

laboratory techniques in which DNA and RNA can be cut, ligated, interconverted and replicated *in vitro*. Coupled with the decreasing cost of sequencing, DNA has become a convenient readout for a variety of molecular biology assays. This started with the development of EST and cDNA technologies, was followed by high-throughput genome sequencing and then progressed through routine large-scale transcriptome sequencing, and finally to yet more intensive processes such as RNA-seq, Chip-seq and DNaseI-seq. We have even witnessed the development of DNA sequencing-based methods with no direct biological role, such as the mathematical exploration of a combinatoric space and the development of unique synthetic tags for property tracking.

DNA sequences determined for research purposes have been routinely archived since 1982, when the EMBL Data Library was founded. This was closely followed by the formation of GenBank first at the US Department of Energy and then transferred to NIH, and in 1987 by the DNA Databank of Japan. These three centres joined to form a tripartite collaboration, the INSDC, to archive and provide access to all DNA sequences generated by publicly funded research [3]. This data archiving project has gone through many changes in its 30-year history, responding both to advances in sequencing technology and to changes in the use of DNA sequence information.

Papers in the era of big-data

goal: Executable Research Objects

July 2012 Wilson GA, Dhimi P, Feber A, Cortázar D, Suzuki Y, Schulz R, Schär P, Beck S: **Resources for methylome analysis suitable for gene knockout studies of potential epigenome modifiers.** *GigaScience* 2012, **1:3.** (*in press*)

GigaDB hosting all data + tools (84GB total): [doi:10.5524/100035](https://doi.org/10.5524/100035)

+

Partial (~80%) integration of workflow into our data platform.
(all the data processing steps, but not the enrichment analysis)

Data in ISA-Tab compliant format

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Papers fully integrating all data + all workflows in our platform.

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